

MAGNETISM AND CATALYSIS. PART III. CHLORINATION OF CHLOROFORM TO CARBON TETRACHLORIDE IN PRESENCE OF FERRIC CHLORIDE.

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The rôle of ferric chloride as an inhibitor in the chlorination of chloroform to carbon tetrachloride has been studied with the help of the magnetic method. The inhibitory action has been observed to be absent if the sample of chloroform be completely free from moisture which in itself has a catalytic effect upon the reaction. The action of ferric chloride has been explained as an outcome of the presence of moisture with which ferric chloride forms a hydrated complex which acts as an inhibitor in this case.

It is well known that if proper precautions are not taken, methane on chlorination yields a number of chloro derivatives which are formed as the result of successive replacement of hydrogen by chlorine in methane. If, however, chloroform alone be chlorinated then carbon tetrachloride is formed. The chlorination of the hydrocarbon is influenced by (i) light, (ii) temperature, and (iii) catalysts. Bedford and collaborators (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1916, 8, 1029, 1091) investigated the influence of light on the chlorination of methane and concluded that a large share of the actinic power of the quartz lamp lies in the ultraviolet rays but that is not required for chlorination process.

Blanc (U. S. P., 1248065, 1917) used light as well as catalysts for the chlorination of saturated hydrocarbons. Gault and Truffault (*Compt. rend.*, 1924, 179, 467) from chlorination of chloroform to carbon tetrachloride observed that the reaction did not take place in the dark and was not influenced up to a wave-length $\lambda=639$; but the reaction commenced in the violet region and was very vigorous in the beginning of the ultraviolet region. The reaction becomes feeble below $\lambda=400$. According to Gault and Truffault (*loc. cit.*) the reaction does not take place at very low temperatures but it commences towards -5° and becomes vigorous between 5° and 10° . Iron perchloride, when used as a catalyst, was found by them to behave as an inhibitor, whereas catalysts like calcium chloride were found to have no influence on the reaction. In explaining the part played by ferric chloride as an inhibitor, they suggested that ferric chloride did not take part in the

reaction, but it simply helped in the absorption of particular wave-lengths of light which determined the chlorination at that temperature. If that be so, then the magnetic property of the chlorinated solution will obey the mixture law, but if ferric chloride takes part in the reaction and a new compound is formed, then its formation in the intermediate stages, even though it may not be revealed by ordinary methods of analysis, would be shown by the magnetic analysis of the chlorinated solution.

The main object of the present investigation is, therefore, to ascertain the rôle of ferric chloride as an inhibitor in this reaction with the help of the magnetic method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The susceptibility values were determined on a modified form of Guoy's balance (*vide supra*). In case of solutions, susceptibility has been calculated with the help of the relation :

$$\chi_{\text{soln}} = \chi_{\text{salt}} \times C_{\text{salt}} + \chi_{\text{solvent}} \times (1 - C_{\text{salt}})$$

The following values of susceptibilities were obtained for the various reagents.

TABLE I.

Reagents.	χ .
Chloroform	-0.517×10^{-8}
Carbon tetrachloride	-0.422
Ferric chloride (solid)	$+82.05$
Ferric hydroxide (solid)	$+157.0$

TABLE II.

Constants.	Prepared sample.	Literature.
χ	-0.545×10^{-8}	$-(0.468-0.588) \times 10^{-8}$
Density	1.5035	1.5264
Refrac. index	1.4429	1.4462
B. P.	64.3°	61.2°.

Pure anhydrous ferric chloride was prepared by passing a stream of dry chlorine over iron filings at a temperature of 800°-900°. The small amounts of ferric chloride used as catalyst could not be determined by ordinary gravimetric or volumetric methods, therefore the quantities were estimated colorimetrically by using 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid as an indicator. The results obtained were further checked by using potassium sulphocyanide as an indicator.

Pure chloroform was prepared from a sample available in the stores by firstly shaking the sample with water to remove traces of alcohol which are often associated with chloroform and then distilling it after having kept

it over fused calcium chloride for forty-eight hours. Various physical constants of the sample, thus obtained, were determined and are tabulated in Table II along with the values given in literature.

The divergence between the observed values and those given in literature for various constants may be due to some water, the presence of which is further supported by the colour imparted by this sample of chloroform to anhydrous copper sulphate.

TABLE III.

FeCl ₃ .	Refractive index.	Susceptibility values of		
		CHCl ₃ .	CHCl ₃ + FeCl ₃ .	CHCl ₃ + FeCl ₃ (calc. on mixture law).
0.0165%	1.4436	-0.526 × 10 ⁻⁶	-0.504 × 10 ⁻⁶	-0.512 × 10 ⁻⁶
0.0165	1.4429	-0.549	-0.524	-0.535
0.0208	1.4429	-0.545	-0.512	-0.527
0.0170	1.4425	-0.553	-0.539	-0.542
0.0338	1.4425	-0.554	-0.527	-0.530

It was further observed (Table III) that when the susceptibility values of solutions of ferric chloride in this sample of chloroform were determined, the observed values did not agree with the values calculated on mixture law assuming that ferric chloride or chloroform did not undergo any change. The observed susceptibility values were always lower than the calculated ones indicating thereby that some compound with higher paramagnetic value was being formed.

Ferric chloride readily undergoes hydrolysis to ferric hydroxide in the presence of moisture and ferric hydroxide is more paramagnetic (+ 157 × 10⁻⁸) than ferric chloride (+ 82.05 × 10⁻⁸). It appears, therefore, that the divergence observed between the calculated and observed values of a solution of ferric chloride in chloroform may probably be due to the formation of more paramagnetic ferric hydroxide due to hydrolysis of ferric chloride.

To remove even the last trace of moisture from chloroform the following method was followed. Chloroform, distilled over fused calcium chloride, was kept over phosphorus pentoxide for a couple of days and then it was filtered and distilled. It was not distilled over phosphorus pentoxide, as there was the danger of the formation of a small quantity of carbonyl chloride. The sample, thus prepared, did not give blue colour with anhydrous copper sulphate and the various physical constants determined for this sample agree well with those given in literature.

TABLE IV.

Constants.	Prepared sample.	Literature.
Magnetic susceptibility	0.517×10^{-8}	$(0.488-0.588) \times 10^{-8}$
Density	1.5259	1.5264
Refractive index	1.4444 (at 28°)	1.4462 (at 20°)
Boiling point	61°	61.2°

When magnetic susceptibility of solutions of freshly prepared anhydrous ferric chloride in pure dry chloroform was determined, the observed and the calculated values agreed well (Table V) indicating that the ferric chloride did not undergo any change.

TABLE V.

FeCl ₃ .	Refractive Index.	Susceptibility values of		
		CHCl ₃ .	CHCl ₃ +FeCl ₃ (obs).	CHCl ₃ +FeCl ₃ (calc.).
0.0182%	1.4444	-0.517×10^{-8}	-0.501×10^{-8}	-0.502×10^{-8}
0.0191	1.4444	-0.517	-0.499	-0.500

Chlorination.

Dry chlorine gas was bubbled simultaneously through two wide-mouthed flasks one containing pure chloroform and the other containing chloroform and small amount of ferric chloride. The flasks were kept in a bath maintained at 5°, since at this temperature maximum amount of chlorination took place. The flow of gas in both the flasks was controlled by a flow meter. After chlorination the excess of chlorine dissolved in solutions had to be removed. Gault and Truffault had suggested the use of mercury and arsenious oxide but these reagents on account of their slight solubility in chloroform could not be used. Therefore displacement of dissolved chlorine by an inert gas such as nitrogen was resorted to. Pure nitrogen, free from moisture, as indicated by anhydrous copper sulphate, was bubbled through the flasks till no iodine was liberated on addition of potassium iodide and potassium fluoride. The samples were then kept in vacuum till further use.

After chlorination amount of carbon tetrachloride formed was determined either by measuring the density or the refractive index of the solution. The susceptibilities were determined on a Guoy's balance and the results are tabulated below.

TABLE VIA.

Chlorination of chloroform containing traces of moisture.

Time.	Mixture after chlorination			Amount of	
	Refrac. index of CHCl_3 .	Refrac. index.	Density.	CHCl_3 .	CCl_4 .
3 hrs.	1'4429	1'4450	1'5392	85'71%	14'29%
6	1'4425	1'4502	1'5782	49'00	51'00
12	1'4429	1'4570	1'6260	4'08	95'92

TABLE VIB.

Chlorination of moist chloroform in presence of ferric chloride.

Time.	Amount of			Mixture after chlorination.	
	FeCl_3 .	CHCl_3 .	CCl_4 .	Refrac. index.	Density.
3 hrs	0'0165%	93'87%	6'13%	1'4438	1'5305
6	0'0338	87'41	12'59	1'4444	1'5373
12	0'0208	78'23	21'77	1'4461	1'5471

TABLE VIC.

Susceptibilities.

Time.	Amount of FeCl_3	χ of pure chloroform.		χ of chloroform and ferric chloride.	
		Before chlorination.	After chlorination.	Before chlorination.	After chlorination.
3 hrs.	0'0165%	$-0'549 \times 10^{-6}$	$-0'540 \times 10^{-6}$	$-0'524 \times 10^{-6}$	$-0'516 \times 10^{-6}$
6	0'0338	$-0'554$	$-0'497$	$-0'530$	$-0'522$
12	0'0208	$-0'545$	$-0'443$	$-0'512$	$-0'495$

In all the three samples chlorinated for different times a definite inhibition of chlorination of chloroform by ferric chloride was observed. After 12 hours the chlorination of chloroform was almost complete (95'92%) in the absence of catalyst while in the presence of ferric chloride only

21.77% of chloroform was transformed to carbon tetrachloride. The carbon tetrachloride obtained by fractional distillation of the mixture of chloroform and carbon tetrachloride had $\chi = 0.438 \times 10^{-6}$, refractive index = 1.4576 and density = 1.6304.

Chlorination of completely moisture-free chloroform was also studied (Table VII).

TABLE VIIA.

Chlorination of completely moisture free chloroform.

Time.	Refractive index of CHCl_3 before chlorination.	Amount of		Mixture after chlorination.	
		CHCl_3 .	CCl_4 .	Refrac. index.	Density.
3 hrs.	1.4444	90.41%	9.59%	1.4458	1.5359
6	1.4444	74.65	25.35	1.4481	1.5529
12	1.4444	43.83	56.17	1.4526	1.5857

TABLE VII B.

Chlorination of moisture-free chloroform in presence of ferric chloride.

Time.	Amount of FeCl_3 .	Amount of		Mixture after chlorination.	
		CHCl_3 .	CCl_4 .	Refrac. index.	Density.
3 hrs.	0.0182%	90.41%	9.59%	1.4458	1.5359
6	0.0191	75.34	24.66	1.4481	1.5521
12	0.0191	43.83	56.17	1.4526	1.5857

TABLE VII C.

Susceptibilities.

Time	Amount of FeCl_3	χ of pure chloroform.		χ of chloroform + ferric chloride.	
		Before chlorination.	After chlorination.	Before chlorination.	After chlorination.
3 hrs.	0.0182%	-0.517×10^{-8}	-0.508×10^{-8}	-0.501×10^{-8}	-0.496×10^{-8}
6	0.0191	-0.517	-0.493	-0.500	-0.480
12	0.0191	-0.517	-0.464	-0.500	-0.457

In these cases it is observed that ferric chloride does not act as an inhibitor and the extent of chlorination both in the presence and absence of catalyst is the same.

DISCUSSION.

From the results tabulated in Tables VIA and VIIA it is clear that moisture acts as catalyst in the chlorination of chloroform to carbon tetrachloride. This observation is in accord with the work of Baker and collaborators (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1886, 47, 349; 1894, 65, 611; 1898, 73, 422; 1925, 127, 1990) who have shown that absence of moisture inhibits many reactions.

Gault and Traffault (*loc.cit.*) in trying to explain the part played by ferric chloride in the reaction under investigation showed that there are certain active radiations that are responsible for the chlorination of chloroform, and the inhibition they ascribed to the absorption of these radiations by ferric chloride. If that were so, the amount of carbon tetrachloride, formed on the chlorination of a sample of pure dry chloroform in the presence of ferric chloride, would have been less than that formed in the absence of ferric chloride, but this is contrary to observations as is clear from Tables VIIA and VIIB.

Results tabulated in Table VI(A—C), however, reveal that chlorination of chloroform containing traces of moisture is retarded in the presence of ferric chloride. Furthermore, the observed susceptibility value of the chlorinated solution does not agree with the susceptibility value calculated according to the mixture law assuming that ferric chloride exists as such in the solution and does not undergo any change.

It may be suggested that a new intermediate compound of ferric chloride with chloroform having susceptibility value different from ferric chloride might have been formed. If that were so, then such a compound ought to have also been formed when pure dry chloroform was chlorinated in presence of ferric chloride and the calculated and observed susceptibility values ought to have been different. But from results given in Table V it is clear that calculated and observed values are in excellent agreement. Hence the possibility of the formation of an intermediate compound of ferric chloride and chloroform from the magnetic data is ruled out.

Ferric chloride may combine with water to form a hydrate or it may react with water in chloroform to form ferric hydroxide and thus the new compound formed may be responsible for the inhibition of the reaction.

Usually the susceptibility value of the hydrates of paramagnetic compounds is less than that of their anhydrous variety. So if FeCl_3 combines with moisture in chloroform and forms a hydrate, which is responsible for inhibition, the observed susceptibility of the solution of ferric chloride in chloroform containing traces of moisture should be more diamagnetic than the calculated value of the solution assuming that ferric chloride in solution exists as such. But from Table III, it is clear that the observed susceptibility value shows the formation of a more paramagnetic compound.

Ferric hydroxide is more paramagnetic than ferric chloride. If susceptibility value of the chlorinated solution of chloroform in the presence of ferric chloride be calculated assuming that whole of ferric chloride is converted to ferric hydroxide, then even the calculated susceptibility value does not agree with the observed value. The observed susceptibility value, however, lies between the susceptibility value calculated on the assumption that whole of ferric chloride exists as such and that calculated on the assumption that the whole of the ferric chloride is converted to ferric hydroxide. It suggests that in chloroform containing traces of moisture, part of the ferric chloride exists as such and part is hydrolysed to ferric hydroxide. The inhibition of this reaction by ferric chloride in presence of moisture, therefore, can be attributed to the formation of ferric hydroxide and not to ferric chloride.

But the fact that passage of dry chlorine for a long time in the solution, which would most probably under the circumstances react with ferric hydroxide and set free ferric chloride and water, does not influence the efficiency of ferric chloride as an inhibitor in the presence of moisture, produces doubt as to the correctness of the formation of ferric hydroxide from ferric chloride.

It seems that ferric chloride combines with water and forms a new complex which is not attacked by chlorine in chloroform and because the complex is more paramagnetic than anhydrous ferric chloride, therefore it is not an ordinary hydrate which would have been less paramagnetic than anhydrous ferric chloride. The inhibition of chlorination of chloroform by ferric chloride, as observed by Gault and Truffault, seems to be due to the fact that their samples of chloroform contained some moisture absorbed which was difficult to detect by ordinary chemical methods and consequently part of the ferric chloride formed the new complex, which was responsible for the observed inhibition.

The rôle of the new complex formed in the reaction can be explained by suggesting that moisture, which, as has been shown to act as a catalyst in the process of chlorination, is removed by ferric chloride and thus the

reaction is inhibited. If that was the only cause then the percentage of carbon tetrachloride formed on chlorination should be either equal to or more than that formed when chloroform containing no moisture is chlorinated, according to whether whole or part of the moisture is removed by ferric chloride.

But actually as it is clear from Tables VI and VII, the percentage of carbon tetrachloride formed by chlorination of pure chloroform is more than that formed on the chlorination of chloroform containing moisture and ferric chloride.

Gault and Truffault, as a result of their investigations attributed inhibition to the absorption of active radiations which favour chlorination of chloroform. It seems, therefore, that besides the removal of the catalyst water by ferric chloride, the absorption of active radiation by the complex which favour chlorination are also responsible for the inhibition of the chlorination of chloroform by ferric chloride as suggested by Gault and Truffault.

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